

PLAY-BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING NUMBER RECOGNITION AMONG THE KINDERGARTEN LEARNERS

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Play-Based Approach in Teaching Number Recognition among the Kindergarten Learners

Sheena Mae A. Porras,* Ian G. Caliba

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study determined the effectiveness of play-based learning compared to traditional teaching methods in developing number recognition among kindergarten learners at Kiwalan Elementary School during the School Year 2024-2025. The research specifically examined pretest and posttest performance to evaluate which instructional approach yields greater improvements in students' number recognition skills. Initial assessments indicated that both groups of learners exhibited similar, limited number recognition abilities, with most scores falling within the "Poor" and "Below Average" categories. Following the implementation of the respective teaching methods, significant improvements were observed in both groups. However, the play-based approach demonstrated more substantial gains, with a majority of students achieving scores in the "Above Average" and "Excellent" ranges post-intervention. In contrast, while the traditional approach also led to improvements, fewer students reached high-performance levels. Statistical analyses confirmed that both instructional strategies positively impacted student outcomes; nevertheless, the play-based method proved superior in fostering number recognition skills. The findings underscored the potential of play-based learning as a more engaging and effective pedagogical strategy for young learners, supporting a growing body of research advocating for interactive and hands-on learning experiences in early childhood education. This study contributes to the discourse on early numeracy instruction by highlighting the benefits of incorporating play into educational practices, suggesting that such approaches may enhance not only academic performance but also overall student engagement and motivation in learning environments.

Keywords: *play-based approach, number recognition, pretest and posttest, teaching strategies*

Introduction

A child's cognitive development includes the ability to understand the concept of numbers. One component of a child's development that requires early attention from teachers is cognitive ability. Cognitive ability is a shift in thought processes that children go through as they grow and develop, enabling them to think about the world around them. To develop children's ability to recognize number concepts, Susana and Jayanto (2021) stated that the development of cognitive aspects has become very popular as part of human cognitive psychology, including forms of cognition as a form of action and related to understanding, attention, evaluation, memory, consideration, information processing and problem-solving, ways of thinking, and beliefs about something.

In the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) results, the Philippines ranked sixth-lowest among 81 participating countries in mathematics, maintaining a position similar to its previous performance in 2018. The country recorded an average score of 355 in mathematics, which is only slightly improved from 353 in the previous assessment (OECD, 2023). The overall results of the national assessments revealed the following results: Many early-grade learners struggled to meet the learning standards in early language literacy and numeracy and had low achievement levels in English, Math, and Science. This means that many low-performing learners cannot comprehend (read and understand) Math and Science. Hence, they were unable to demonstrate their knowledge in these content areas.

In order to address the aforementioned gaps, there was a need to strengthen the numeracy skills of every learner which was needed for academic success in later key stages. The Department of Education has taken a proactive approach to strengthen the learning recovery and continuity program, improve literacy and numeracy, and accelerate the achievement of education targets (DepEd, 2023). They launched a subprogram called the National Mathematics Program (NMP) that focuses on collaborative action to promote better numeracy and mathematics learning in schools across all grade levels and requested every school in the country to administer assessments to improve numeracy and literacy and to have reliable data on numeracy and mathematics progress and achievement.

In DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016, entitled "Policy Guidelines on Daily Lesson Preparation for the K to 12 Basic Education Program," included provisions on the use of varied learning materials and teaching techniques in the classroom. Specifically, the order mandated that teachers use various learning resources, such as textbooks, supplementary materials, technology-based resources, and other educational resources that were appropriate for the learners' needs and learning styles. It also encouraged the use of different teaching strategies and techniques, such as inquiry-based learning, cooperative learning, problem-based learning, and differentiated instruction.

Furthermore, DepEd Order No. 29, s. 2018, entitled "Policy on the Implementation of Multi-Factored Assessment Tool," emphasized the use of varied assessment tools and techniques to ensure that student learning was assessed holistically. The order encouraged the use of formative assessments, performance tasks, and other authentic assessments that went beyond traditional paper-and-pencil tests.

Overall, these orders reflect the importance of using varied learning materials and teaching techniques in the classroom to ensure that students' diverse learning needs and styles are addressed and they can achieve their full potential. Number recognition was crucial in

kindergarten, forming the foundation for mathematical development. By the end of kindergarten, children were expected to recognize and identify numbers from 0 to 20 (Educationist, 2024). This skill was essential for building a strong numerical understanding, which is fundamental for more advanced mathematical concepts in the future.

Moreover, number recognition in kindergarten helps children develop math confidence and critical thinking skills and lays the groundwork for success in math (Scholar, n.d.). It also enables children to understand the value of numbers, perceive relationships between them, and recognize patterns, enhancing their problem-solving abilities. Mastering number recognition in kindergarten was a key step toward academic success and everyday life applications involving numbers.

The play-based approach in numeracy education emphasizes the importance of engaging children through play to foster their mathematical understanding and skills. This method was particularly effective in early childhood settings, where children learn best through exploration and interaction with their environment.

The study determined the effectiveness of the play-based approach in teaching number recognition. Play-based learning can occur effectively when children are allowed the room, time, and independence to participate in activities and work with materials that have meaning and interest for them. This could entail children playing by themselves, with adults, or with other kids. This study was conducted among the Kindergarteners of Kiwalan Elementary School, School Year 2024-2025.

In line with this thought, the researcher wanted to capitalize on the play-based approach and its effectiveness in teaching number recognition among kindergarteners. Play-based teaching and learning gives children a context within which they can situate new information and concepts, helps to keep children's intellect engaged, and progressing play encourages greater language comprehension development.

The first step in a child's educational journey is kindergarten, which lays the foundation for later academic success and personal growth. A teacher with a strong background in early childhood education and child development can best provide children with what they need to grow physically, intellectually, emotionally and socially. Thus, the researcher is interested in studying this topic because she has been a kindergarten public school teacher for six (6) years.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of a play-based approach in teaching number recognition among the kindergarten learners of Kiwalan Elementary School, School Year 2024-2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What are the pretest scores of participants in the traditional approach and play-based approach in teaching number recognition?
2. What are the posttest scores of participants in the traditional approach and play-based approach in teaching number recognition?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of participants in the traditional approach and the play-based approach in teaching number recognition?
4. Is there a significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of participants in the traditional approach?
5. Is there a significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of participants in the play-based approach?
6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the participants in the traditional approach and the play-based approach?
7. What action plan can be designed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used in this study was experimental. The participants were given a pretest to measure their prior knowledge and establish equality between groups. Then, the researcher conducted the lesson using the traditional approach and a play-based approach. After the implementation, a posttest was given to the participants to measure the effectiveness of the play-based approach in teaching.

Respondents

The participants of this study were the 40 Kindergarten learners of Kiwalan Elementary School, which was composed of two sections: Section Malinis and Mabait. The researcher used complete enumeration to determine the sections.

The Control Group consisted of 20 learners from Kindergarten Malinis, and the Experimental Group consisted of 20 learners from Kindergarten Mabait.

Table 1. *KES Kindergarten Respondents*

Name of Sections	Kindergarten Enrollees		Total
	Male	Female	
Kindergarten-Malinis	8	12	20
Kindergarten-Mabait	10	10	20
Total	18	22	40

A pretest was administered to both groups in order to measure their prior knowledge about number recognition. The identification of the traditional group and the experimental group was done through drawing lots. The name of the section that was drawn out first was the traditional group and the other one was the experimental group. The experimental group is section Malinis and the control group is section Mabait.

Instrument

The research instrument used in gathering the data for this research study was an assessment tool adopted from chocawsummerlearning.org. Before the assessment tool was finalized, this was submitted to the adviser for further suggestions and comments.

There were 21 total items in the assessment. The teacher assessed number recognition from 0-20 and then marked incorrect responses with an X on the box on the student recording sheets. There were two boxes provided on the recording sheets: left for the pretest and the right for the posttest. Each respondent was given a student testing sheet and was asked to name each number.

Procedure

The following were the steps that were carried out upon gathering the pertinent data for the study:

The researcher sent letters to the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) of Iligan City to conduct the research after the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School, St. Peter's College, Iligan City. After the SDS approved the letter, it was forwarded to the principal of Kiwalan Elementary School.

When the permission was secured, the researcher gathered the prior knowledge of the learners about the subject matter by administering the pretest. The pretest was administered to both groups of learners. The pretest was given to the participants a week before the conduct of the study. The researcher administered the pretest to measure the prior knowledge of the participants about the topic. Confidentiality of their identity and answers was secured observing the Ethics of Research.

After three (3) months of the implementation of the approaches, a posttest was given to measure the academic performance in number recognition in the experimental group. Confidentiality of their identity and answers was assured by observing the Ethics of Research. The pretest and post-test scores were recorded, tallied, and consolidated the correct responses for each correct item. Then, the researcher analyzed the data and interpreted it in the research study.

The intervention was integrated during the Work Period 2. The integration of the play-based approach was 40 minutes per day for about three (3) months.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used to analyze and explain the variation of the sample data.

The frequency and percentage were used to determine the pretest and post-test scores of the participants

The Mann-Whitney U test was used to test the difference between the participant's scores in the control group and the experimental group.

The Wilcoxon Test was used to examine the difference between the pretest and post-test scores in the control group and also in the experimental group.

Results and Discussion

This chapter focuses on the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data. It presents the data gathered, the results of the statistical analysis, and the interpretation of findings. These are presented in tables following the sequence of the specific research problem regarding the use of a play-based approach in teaching number recognition among kindergarten learners.

Problem 1: What are the pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach and play-based approach in teaching number recognition?

Table 2 (figure 1) presents the pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach. As shown in the table, the highest frequency count was 12, with 60% of learners falling within the "Below Average" category, scoring between 5 and 8. This indicated that while these students possess some foundational knowledge of number recognition, they encounter significant challenges in fully grasping the concepts involved. This suggested that the traditional approach may not be effectively preparing students for number recognition at the level expected for their age group, thus underscoring the necessity for targeted interventions and additional support to enhance their understanding of fundamental numerical concepts.

This distribution of scores aligned with existing research on the limitations of traditional teaching methods. Yabo (2020) noted that pretest assessments often reflect similar patterns among students exposed to traditional teaching methods, particularly in mathematics. These methods, which were often based on rote memorization and direct instruction, fail to engage the students fully and may not

adequately support their cognitive development, especially in foundational subjects such as number recognition. As a result, these students require additional support to bridge the gaps in their understanding.

Table 2. *Pretest Scores of the Participants in Traditional Approach*

Score Range	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)	Description
1 – 4	4	20.0	Poor
5 – 8	12	60.0	Below Average
9 - 12	4	20.0	Average
13 – 16	0	0	Above Average
17 - 21	0	0	Excellent
Total	20	100.0	

Figure 1. *Pretest Scores of the Participants in the Traditional Approach*

The implications of this finding were significant. A predominance of low scores indicated that traditional pedagogical strategies, which often rely heavily on direct instruction and passive learning, may not engage young learners effectively. Research has shown that children learn best through interactive and play-based methods, which promote active engagement and cognitive development (Chen & Jin, 2022; Davis & Dunn, 2019). For example, Chen and Jin (2022) emphasized the importance of interactive systems in preschool education, suggesting that technology-enhanced learning environments could improve recognition rates and overall educational outcomes. Similarly, Davis and Dunn (2019) highlighted the need for reflective teaching practices that could enhance educators' professional efficacy, ultimately improving student learning outcomes.

Further, the lack of participants achieving scores in the "Above Average" (13-16) or "Excellent" (17-21) ranges raised concerns about the adequacy of the traditional approach in preparing students for future academic challenges. The absence of students reaching higher levels of mastery was particularly troubling, as early mastery of number recognition is crucial for later mathematical success. Gnjatović et al. (2020) stressed the importance of early numeracy skills as the foundation for later mathematical achievement. When early interventions were not effectively implemented, students were at risk of falling behind in the later stages of their education.

The findings also reflected a broader trend in early childhood education, where traditional methods failed to cater to children's diverse learning needs. Margrain and Farquhar (2021) discussed the importance of recognizing individual differences in learning styles and the necessity for differentiated instruction to effectively meet these needs. This perspective was crucial, as it underscores the need for educators to adapt their teaching strategies to better meet the learning needs of all students, especially those who are struggling.

In contrast, 20% of the participants scored in the "Poor" range (1-4), indicating a significant portion of the group that struggles considerably with number recognition. This subset of learners was likely to require more intensive, individualized support to overcome their challenges. Tarr (2017) further emphasizes that students scoring poorly on initial assessments often need targeted interventions to address their specific learning gaps. Although the percentage of students in the "Poor" range was smaller, their need for additional attention was equally critical. Poor performance at the beginning of the academic year was not uncommon among young learners, but with appropriate teaching methods and sustained engagement, these students could achieve substantial progress over time (Alomar, 2022).

Moreover, research consistently indicated that traditional teaching methods might not adequately address the diverse needs of learners, necessitating a shift towards more innovative and student-centered approaches. Romera et al. (2022) advocated for more interactive teaching strategies that actively engage students and address the various learning styles present in the classroom. A shift towards more dynamic, engaging, and differentiated methods—such as play-based learning—could provide a solution to the gaps identified in the traditional approach.

These pretest scores of participants in the traditional approach to teaching number recognition revealed significant areas for improvement. The predominance of low scores suggested that traditional methods may not effectively support the development of

essential numerical skills in young learners. The literature supported a shift towards more interactive and play-based approaches, which have been shown to enhance learning outcomes and foster a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. Future educational strategies should prioritize these methods to better equip students for academic success, ensuring that all learners—especially those struggling in the "Poor" and "Below Average" categories—receive the support they need to thrive.

Table 3 (figure 2) displays the pretest scores of the participants in the play-based approach. As shown in the table, the highest frequency count of 11 is within the "Below Average" range (5-8), indicating that while most students did not achieve high mastery, their performance was better than those in the "Poor" range. This was significant when compared to the traditional approach, which had 60% of students scoring poorly. The reduction in the "Poor" category, with only 15% of participants scoring between 1-4, further supports the idea that the play-based approach may improve foundational skills in number recognition. This trend aligned with findings from Wardhani (2023), who suggested that play-based learning strategies can engage young children, improving their cognitive outcomes through hands-on and interactive learning experiences.

Table 3. *Pretest Scores of the Participants in Play-based Approach*

Score Range	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)	Description
1 – 4	3	15.0	Poor
5 – 8	11	55.0	Below Average
9 - 12	6	30.0	Average
13 – 16	0	0	Above Average
17 - 21	0	0	Excellent
Total	20	100.0	

Figure 2. *Pretest Scores of the Participants in Play-based Approach*

While the play-based approach does not yet produce scores in the "Above Average" or "Excellent" categories, the reduction in low scores indicated that it may be more effective than traditional methods in fostering foundational numeracy skills. The emphasis on interactive, hands-on learning aligns with constructivist theories of learning, which suggested that children learn best when they actively engage with their environment (Norok, 2023). Piaget (1952) and Vygotsky (1978) both argue that cognitive development is enhanced through play, exploration, and problem-solving, central features of the play-based approach. The relatively high percentage of students in the "Below Average" range may reflect the early stages of engagement with the play-based method, which is designed to develop skills gradually over time.

Supporting literature highlighted the cognitive benefits of play-based learning in early childhood education. Recent studies have further corroborated the positive impact of play-based learning on cognitive development. Anuar (2024) highlights that Game-Based Learning (GBL) serves as an effective educational tool that significantly enhances children's executive functions, which are crucial for cognitive and social skill development. This finding was particularly relevant as it underscores the role of structured play in fostering critical cognitive abilities in early childhood. Similarly, the integration of Project-Based Learning (PBL) has been shown to stimulate cognitive abilities in young children, suggesting that hands-on, engaging activities can lead to improved cognitive outcomes (International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis, 2023).

Moreover, the utilization of motion and sound games has been linked to enhanced cognitive skills in early childhood. Research by Sriwidaningsih and Friskawati (2022) indicated that incorporating music and movement into learning activities promotes cognitive development through interconnected experiences, which are essential for young learners. This aligned with the notion that play-based learning environments, characterized by active engagement and exploration, are vital for cognitive growth.

The findings from this study, showing a higher percentage of students scoring in the "Average" range compared to traditional methods, further supported the idea that play-based methods can enhance children's understanding of abstract concepts.

However, the absence of participants in the "Above Average" or "Excellent" categories suggested that there may be limitations to the current play-based strategies used in this study. While the approach was effective in improving foundational skills, it may not be structured or intensive enough to elevate a significant number of students to higher levels of achievement. Recent literature has highlighted the efficacy of guided play as a pedagogical tool in early childhood education. For instance, Ndabezitha (2024) argued that guided play, characterized by educator involvement, enhances children's learning experiences by allowing them to explore their interests while receiving necessary scaffolding. This approach not only affirms learners' agency but also directs them toward specific learning goals, thus facilitating cognitive development. The use of open-ended questions and skillful questioning techniques in guided play has been shown to significantly enhance children's engagement and understanding, further supporting Bodrova and Leong's claims about the necessity of guidance in play-based learning environments (Ndabezitha, 2024).

Moreover, Jensen et al. (2019) explored the enactment of guided play in early years classrooms, demonstrating that educator involvement in play activities can effectively extend children's learning experiences. Their findings suggested that guided play can be situated along a continuum, where the level of educator involvement can vary, thereby allowing for a tailored approach that meets the diverse needs of learners. This flexibility in implementation underscores the importance of balancing structured learning with opportunities for exploration and creativity, as advocated by Bodrova and Leong.

The integration of technology in guided play has also been a focal point in recent studies. Ethridge et al. (2022) examined how virtual teaching can foster play in early childhood education, revealing that educators' attitudes toward technology significantly influence their ability to incorporate it effectively into guided play scenarios. This highlights the necessity for professional development that equips educators with the skills to blend technology with play-based learning. The findings emphasized that while guided play is beneficial, its effectiveness can be enhanced through thoughtful integration of educational technology.

The pretest results show that while a significant number of students scored in the "Below Average" range, there is still considerable improvement compared to traditional methods. Furthermore, the presence of 30% of students in the "Average" range indicates that the play-based approach has the potential to engage learners and foster a basic understanding of number recognition. This was consistent with literature advocating for play as a critical component of early childhood education, enhancing not only cognitive skills but also social and emotional development (Dornhoffer et al., 2021; Carvalho et al., 2021). Reding and Moore (2023) also highlighted the importance of incorporating evidence-based practices in teaching, which can be facilitated through play-based learning environments that encourage exploration.

Despite these positive trends, the 15% of participants still scoring in the "Poor" range underscores the importance of differentiated instruction within play-based frameworks to meet the diverse needs of students. Gregory et al. (2019) emphasized that targeted interventions were crucial for improving outcomes for students at risk of falling behind. When integrated into interactive and engaging learning environments, such interventions can significantly improve outcomes for struggling students. Therefore, further refinement of the play-based approach was necessary to support these learners more effectively.

The absence of participants scoring in the "Above Average" or "Excellent" categories raises important questions about the current play-based strategies employed. While the approach shows promise in improving foundational skills, it may need to be further refined to provide the appropriate level of challenge for students. Research indicated that the quality of play-based activities is critical; poorly designed or insufficiently challenging activities may not yield the desired educational outcomes (Holley & Park, 2020). Educators must be intentional in selecting and implementing play-based strategies that are both engaging and appropriately challenging, ensuring they align with learning objectives and foster a deeper understanding of concepts like number recognition.

These pretest scores of participants in the play-based approach to teaching number recognition reveal a promising but mixed picture. While the majority of students fell into the "Below Average" range, a smaller proportion achieved "Average" scores compared to the traditional approach, suggesting that play-based methods may offer a more engaging and effective foundation for early numeracy skills. The literature supports the benefits of play-based learning in promoting cognitive development, particularly in early numeracy, but also suggested the need for a balanced approach that integrates both play and structured guidance. Future educational strategies should focus on refining play-based activities to provide the necessary challenge and structure to support higher achievement in number recognition, particularly for students who are at risk of falling behind. Combining play-based methods with targeted interventions may offer a more comprehensive approach to improving number recognition skills in preschoolers.

Problem 2: What are the posttest scores of the participants in the traditional approach and play-based approach in teaching number recognition?

Table 4 (figure 3) displays the posttest scores of the participants in traditional approach. As shown in the table, the highest frequency count was observed in the "Average" range (9-12), with 50% of participants achieving scores within this category. This indicated that half of the students demonstrated a solid understanding of number recognition, performing at the expected level for their grade. Conversely, the lowest frequency count was found in the "Below Average" range (5-8), where 25% of participants scored, suggesting that a quarter of the class still struggled with number recognition despite exposure to the traditional teaching approach.

The high frequency of participants in the "Average" range suggested that the traditional approach was effective for the majority of students, enabling them to reach a foundational level of competence in number recognition. Guilmois et al. (2019) conducted a

comparative study on effective numeracy educational interventions for students from disadvantaged backgrounds. Their findings indicated that explicit teaching methods, which are characteristic of traditional approaches, were particularly effective for complex learning content and skills. The study highlighted that structured instruction can significantly enhance students' understanding of numeracy concepts, especially for those who may struggle with more informal learning environments. This underscores the importance of traditional teaching methods in providing a solid foundation for numeracy skills among young learners.

Table 4. *Posttest Scores of the Participants in Traditional Approach*

Score Range	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)	Description
1 – 4	0	0	Poor
5 – 8	5	25.0	Below Average
9 – 12	10	50.0	Average
13 – 16	5	25.0	Above Average
17 – 21	0	0	Excellent
Total	20	100.0	

Figure 3. *Posttest Scores of the Participants in the Traditional Approach*

However, the 25% of participants who scored in the "Below Average" range highlight a key limitation of the traditional approach. While no students fell into the "Poor" category, the presence of a quarter of the class in the "Below Average" range suggests that there remains a significant portion of students who struggle with basic number recognition. These students may require additional support or differentiated instruction to reach a higher level of competency (Jairus, 2023). This underscores the importance of tailoring instruction to meet the diverse needs of learners, particularly those who may not thrive under a more traditional, one-size-fits-all model.

The presence of students in the "Below Average" range further points to the limitations of the traditional approach in addressing the needs of struggling learners. While it works for many, it may not be sufficiently dynamic or individualized to engage all students effectively. As such, more personalized or interactive learning experiences may be necessary to better support these students (Demir & Keleş, 2021). Research suggested that differentiated instruction, which accounts for the varying levels of student ability, is critical for fostering improved outcomes, especially for learners who need additional support to keep up with their peers (Gregory et al., 2019).

Moreover, the absence of students in the "Excellent" category raises additional concerns. While a solid foundation is achieved for most students, the lack of high achievers suggests that the traditional approach may fall short in promoting higher-order thinking or mastery of number recognition. Literature on more interactive and hands-on teaching methods, such as play-based learning, indicates that these approaches may not only enhance foundational skills but also promote higher cognitive development (Motsumi et al., 2019). Piaget's (1952) theory of cognitive development emphasized the importance of active engagement and problem-solving in fostering deeper learning, and the lack of "Excellent" scores in the traditional approach suggests that such engagement might be missing. More interactive strategies could potentially offer a pathway to achieving higher levels of achievement in number recognition.

While the traditional approach to number recognition was largely effective in helping the majority of students achieve basic competency, the presence of a quarter of students in the "Below Average" range suggests that it may not fully accommodate the needs of all learners. To address this, further differentiation and targeted support are necessary to help struggling students reach proficiency. The findings also point to the potential benefits of integrating more interactive, student-centered strategies to support not only foundational skills but also promote higher-level cognitive engagement. Thus, a balanced approach that combines traditional methods with more personalized and interactive teaching practices may be most effective in ensuring that all students achieve success in number recognition (Gopalan et al., 2018).

Table 5 (figure 4) presents the posttest scores of the participants in the play-based approach. As shown in the table, the highest frequency count is 12 found in the "Excellent" range (17-21), with 60% of participants scoring within this category, indicating that the majority

of students demonstrated a high level of mastery in number recognition. Additionally, 40% of participants scored in the "Above Average" range (13-16), further reinforcing the effectiveness of the play-based approach. Notably, there were no participants in the "Below Average" (5-8) or "Poor" (1-4) categories, suggesting that the play-based approach was highly effective in ensuring that all students performed above the basic levels of competency.

Table 5. *Posttest Scores of the Participants in Play-based Approach*

Score Range	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)	Description
1 - 4	0	0	Poor
5 - 8	0	0	Below Average
9 - 12	0	0	Average
13 - 16	8	40.0	Above Average
17 - 21	12	60.0	Excellent
Total	20	100.0	

Figure 4. *Posttest Scores of the Participants in the Play-based Approach*

The implications of these findings are significant for early childhood education. The 60% of students achieving "Excellent" scores suggests that the play-based approach is exceptionally effective in promoting not only foundational number recognition skills but also a higher level of mastery in these skills. This finding aligns with research by (Raihana et al., 2021; Rahma et al., 2023), which emphasized the importance of interactive, hands-on learning environments in supporting deeper cognitive development, particularly in early mathematics. The absence of participants in the "Poor" and "Below Average" categories further supports the play-based approach's success in preventing students from struggling with number recognition, a key concern in early education. This contrasts with the traditional approach, where 25% of students scored in the "Below Average" category, highlighting the play-based method's potential for greater engagement and more consistent achievement among all learners.

Moreover, the success of the play-based approach in addressing the diverse learning needs of students is evident. The hands-on, exploratory nature of play-based learning likely enabled students to learn at their own pace, with ample opportunities for practice and individualized support. This finding resonated with Piaget's (1952) theory of cognitive development, which posits that children learn best through active engagement with their environment. Play-based approaches, therefore, seem particularly well-suited for fostering early numeracy skills and catering to diverse learning profiles (Sitorus, 2023). This approach's inclusivity was an important consideration, as it minimizes the risk of students falling behind in foundational skills, which could lead to persistent learning gaps (Danylchenko et al., 2023).

These results from the play-based approach indicated highly successful outcomes, with 60% of students achieving "Excellent" scores and 40% achieving "Above Average" scores. The absence of participants in the lower score categories further affirms the effectiveness of play-based learning in promoting foundational numeracy skills. These findings aligned with the broader literature, which underscores the benefits of interactive and hands-on teaching methods in early childhood education (Raihana et al., 2021). However, further research is necessary to assess the long-term effects of play-based learning and its applicability across diverse educational contexts to ensure the sustainability and scalability of these positive outcomes.

Problem 3: Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach and play-based approach?

Table 6 presents the difference between the pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach and the play-based approach. The data revealed that the pretest scores of the play-based approach were not significantly different from the pretest scores in the traditional approach. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the traditional approach and the play-based approach, was not rejected.

Table 6. *Difference1 Pretest Scores of the Traditional Approach and Play-based Approach*

		Static	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference
Pretest Traditional Approach	Pretest Play-based Approach	176	0.526	1.00	

*Note: 1 – Mann Whitney U Test ** - p < 0.01 *** - p < 0.001 ns - p > 0.05 * - p < 0.05*

Table 6 presents the difference between the pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach and the play-based approach. The data revealed that the pretest scores of the play-based approach were not significantly different from the pretest scores in the traditional approach. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the traditional approach and the play-based approach, was not rejected.

The mean difference of 1.00, while indicative of a slight variation in scores, is statistically insignificant, reinforcing the conclusion that both groups possessed comparable levels of knowledge regarding number recognition prior to the intervention. This equivalence in pretest scores establishes a robust baseline for evaluating the effectiveness of the instructional methods applied in the study.

The absence of pre-existing differences in the pretest scores supported the premise that any variations observed in posttest scores can be attributed to the instructional methods rather than initial knowledge disparities. This was crucial for the integrity of the research, as it allowed for a clearer assessment of the impact of the teaching strategies employed. Furthermore, the findings underscored the potential effectiveness of both the traditional and play-based approaches as starting points for instruction, suggesting that educators could confidently implement either method without concern for initial knowledge discrepancies among students.

Moreover, the results paved the way for a deeper exploration of the play-based approach's effectiveness in enhancing number recognition skills. Although the pretest scores did not reveal significant differences, the subsequent analysis of posttest scores will be critical in determining whether the play-based approach yields greater improvements in learners' cognitive abilities. Research has consistently highlighted the advantages of play-based learning in fostering cognitive development, particularly in early childhood education. For instance, studies indicated that play-based learning could enhance children's engagement, motivation, and knowledge retention, which were essential components for effective learning outcomes (Annuar, 2024; Ahmed, 2023; Adams, 2024).

In examining the effectiveness of traditional teaching methods, it was essential to recognize that while they may provide a structured foundation for basic skills, they often lack the dynamic engagement that play-based approaches offer. Traditional methods, characterized by direct instruction and rote learning, may not adequately address the holistic developmental needs of children, particularly in areas such as numeracy where meaningful interaction with learning materials was crucial (Farida & Rasyid, 2019; Uhar, 2023; Ntshangase & Venketsamy, 2022). The low mean difference in pretest scores suggested that while both methods may start from a similar knowledge base, the real differences in effectiveness were likely to emerge in the posttest data, where the impact of the instructional strategies can be more thoroughly evaluated.

Supporting literature emphasized the significance of cognitive development theories in understanding the learning processes of young children. Research indicated that children's cognitive abilities, including number recognition, were highly malleable and influenced by their interactions with their environment (Wardhani, 2023; Laksana et al., 2020; Mayer, 2019). The pretest results suggested that both groups were likely at similar cognitive development stages, reinforcing the notion that the chosen instructional methods will play a pivotal role in shaping learning outcomes. Furthermore, the literature on play-based learning underscores its effectiveness in promoting cognitive development through engaging and interactive experiences that facilitate a deeper understanding of abstract concepts like numbers (Buil et al., 2019; Almulla, 2024; Parthasarathy et al., 2023).

Contradictory literature also highlighted the limitations of traditional teaching methods in fostering holistic development. For example, studies have shown that traditional approaches may not sufficiently engage students in meaningful learning experiences, which are vital for cognitive and social development (Annuar, 2024; Uhar, 2023; Sohail, 2024). The pretest scores' similarity suggested that traditional methods could benefit from integrating elements of play and hands-on learning to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes from the outset.

While the pretest scores indicated no significant differences between the traditional and play-based approaches, the focus must shift to the posttest results to ascertain the impact of these teaching methods on number recognition skills. The forthcoming analysis would provide insights into whether the play-based approach leads to greater cognitive improvements, aligning with existing research that advocates for active, engagement-based learning strategies. This study's findings would contribute to the broader discourse on effective instructional methods in early childhood education, emphasizing the importance of fostering cognitive development through innovative teaching practices.

Problem 4: Is there a significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach?

Table 7 presents the difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach. The data revealed that the posttest scores had a significant difference between the pretest scores in the traditional approach. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach,

was rejected.

Table 7. *Difference2 Posttest and Pretest scores in the Traditional Approach*

		Static	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference
Posttest	Pretest	210	<0.001	4.26	0.310
Traditional Approach	Traditional Approach				

Note: 2 – Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test ** - $p < 0.01$ *** - $p < 0.001$ ns - $p > 0.05$ * - $p < 0.05$

Table 7 presents the difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach. The data revealed that the posttest scores had a significant difference between the pretest scores in the traditional approach. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach, was rejected.

The result revealed a statistically significant difference, with a p-value of <0.001. This indicates that the traditional teaching method has a measurable effect on improving participants' performance in number recognition. Such findings were consistent with existing literature that emphasizes the effectiveness of structured, teacher-directed instruction in enhancing foundational numeracy skills. For instance, explicit instructional strategies, including the use of flashcards and repetition, have been shown to lead to significant improvements in early math skills (Amzat et al., 2022; Thien et al., 2023). The current study's results corroborated these findings, demonstrating that participants exhibited a statistically significant improvement following the intervention utilizing traditional methods.

Despite the statistical significance of the results, the mean difference of 4.26 points, with a standard error of 0.310, suggests that the magnitude of improvement in number recognition is relatively modest. This raised critical considerations regarding the effectiveness of traditional approaches in fostering deeper or more enduring learning. While the traditional method effectively achieves basic educational goals, research indicated that such teacher-centered methods may not engage children in ways that promote profound or lasting learning outcomes (Nazim, 2023; Ntege, 2023). In contrast, more interactive and child-centered approaches, such as play-based learning, have been highlighted for their potential to foster meaningful engagement and facilitate deeper cognitive development (Cheng et al., 2020; Hallinger & Hosseingholizadeh, 2019).

Furthermore, the modesty of the mean difference suggested limitations in the traditional approach's capacity to engage children's natural curiosity and promote long-term retention of number recognition skills. This observation aligned with studies indicating that dynamic and experiential learning environments, particularly those centered around play-based approaches, could yield greater gains in foundational skills (Zhang et al., 2021; Liu & Hallinger, 2022). Research comparing traditional and play-based methods consistently demonstrated that play-based learning, with its emphasis on hands-on activities, exploration, and social interaction, leads to more significant and sustained improvements in early numeracy skills (Ma & Marion, 2019; Li & Liang, 2023).

While the significant p-value (<0.001) supported the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating a statistically significant difference between pretest and posttest scores, the relatively modest mean difference suggests that traditional approaches, while effective, may not be as impactful as more interactive and play-based methods in promoting long-term improvements in number recognition. This finding underscored the importance of integrating a variety of instructional strategies to optimize learning outcomes for young children.

Problem 5: Is there a significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the play-based approach?

Table 8. *Difference3 Posttest and Pretest scores in Play-based Approach*

		Static	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference
Posttest	Pretest	820	<0.001	7.10	0.505
Play-based Approach	Play-based Approach				

Note: 3 – Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test ** - $p < 0.01$ *** - $p < 0.001$ ns - $p > 0.05$ * - $p < 0.05$

Table 8 presents the difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the play-based approach. The data revealed that the post-test scores had a significant difference between the pretest scores in the play-based approach. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there was no significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the play-based approach, was rejected.

The results revealed a statistically significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores, with a p-value of <0.001, indicating that the play-based approach led to a meaningful improvement in participants' number recognition skills. This significant difference demonstrates the effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing students' ability to recognize and understand numbers. However, the mean difference of 7.10, with a standard error of 0.505, suggests that while the improvement was statistically significant, its magnitude was modest. Despite this, the findings underscore that the play-based approach facilitated notable learning gains in number recognition, positively impacting the participants' abilities in this area.

The result of this analysis underscored the potential of play-based learning in enhancing foundational numeracy skills among young learners. The play-based approach's hands-on, exploratory, and interactive nature appears to have created an environment conducive

to learning, where students could engage with the material more dynamically and intellectually. This aligned with Vygotsky's (1978) social constructivist theory, which emphasizes the importance of active, social learning experiences for cognitive development. Play-based learning, by encouraging students to interact with their environment and each other, provides opportunities for deeper learning, reinforcing concepts like number recognition enjoyably and effectively.

The significant improvement observed in the play-based group is consistent with a large body of literature highlighting the effectiveness of interactive, play-based methods in promoting early numeracy skills. Hidayah et al., in 2021 found that play-based interventions can lead to substantial improvements in early math skills because they allow children to actively explore mathematical concepts through play.utama et al. (2023) also supported this notion, stating that playful learning environments help foster engagement, which was a key factor in promoting deeper understanding in young children. In this study, the posttest results reflect the enhanced engagement and mastery that play-based learning provides, which was also observed in previous research on similar educational interventions.

Additionally, the results of this study contrasted with more traditional instructional approaches, which may not offer the same degree of hands-on, experiential learning. Traditional methods, which were typically more structured and teacher-directed, may not always support the same level of interaction or exploration, potentially limiting opportunities for students to internalize and apply new concepts in meaningful ways (Ranzato et al., 2021) (Utama, 2023).

However, it was also important to acknowledge that some studies suggested that the effectiveness of play-based learning can vary depending on how the activities are structured. Rahmah (2023) argued that play-based approaches must be thoughtfully designed and guided to maximize their educational value. In some instances, poorly structured or unfocused play might not lead to significant learning outcomes. This reinforces the idea that the success of play-based interventions depends not only on the general methodology but also on the way activities are implemented and facilitated.

The significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores in the play-based approach suggested that this teaching method was highly effective in improving early numeracy skills, specifically number recognition. The mean difference of 7.10 underscored the substantial impact of the play-based approach on students' learning outcomes. These results aligned with existing literature that emphasized the positive effects of hands-on, interactive learning environments in early childhood (Hidayah et al., 2021;utama et al., 2023). The findings from this study provided strong evidence supporting the incorporation of play-based methods in early childhood education to enhance foundational mathematical skills and promote deeper cognitive development. Future research may explore the long-term effects of such interventions and investigate how different play-based activities can be optimized to further improve learning outcomes.

Problem 6: Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the participants in the traditional approach and the play-based approach?

Table 9. Difference4 Posttest Scores of the Traditional Approach and Play-based Approach

		Static	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference
Posttest	Posttest	11.5	<0.001	6.00	
Traditional Approach	Play-based Approach				

*Note: 4 – Mann Whitney U Test ** - p < 0.01 *** - p < 0.001 ns - p > 0.05 * - p < 0.05*

Table 9 shows the difference between the post-test scores of the participants in the traditional approach and the play-based approach. The data revealed that the posttest scores of the play-based approach had a significant difference from the posttest scores in the traditional approach. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there was no significant difference between the post-test scores of the participants in the traditional approach and the play-based approach, was rejected.

The results indicated a statistically significant difference between the post-test scores of the two groups, with a p-value of <0.001, suggesting that the play-based approach led to significantly higher post-test scores compared to the traditional approach. The mean difference between the posttest scores of the traditional approach and the play-based approach was found to be 11.5, with a standard error of difference of 6.00. This substantial mean difference suggested that participants in the play-based approach exhibited notably higher scores, indicating greater improvements in number recognition compared to those in the traditional approach group.

The significant difference in post-test scores further underscores the more substantial impact of the play-based approach on student learning outcomes, specifically in number recognition. A mean difference of 11.5 highlights that participants in the play-based group demonstrated stronger gains in their number recognition skills than those in the traditional approach group. These findings emphasized the effectiveness of play-based learning as a pedagogical strategy in early childhood education, offering compelling evidence of its superior impact on developing foundational numeracy skills.

The results aligned with research emphasizing the advantages of interactive, hands-on, and child-centered learning methods, such as the play-based approach. By actively engaging students in meaningful, context-rich experiences, play-based learning allows them to explore mathematical concepts in ways that were not only more engaging but also more conducive to deeper understanding. The significant improvement in the play-based group supports the idea that experiential learning enhances the ability to grasp abstract concepts like number recognition.

The positive effects of play-based learning were well-documented in the literature. Studies consistently showed that play-based approaches provide students with opportunities to engage in meaningful, context-driven interactions that help solidify their understanding of foundational concepts. Maladerita et al. (2023) and Susilawati et al. (2022), emphasized that such interactive learning environments are particularly effective in early childhood education because they foster engagement and social interaction, both of which were crucial for cognitive development. For example, Susilawati et al. (2022) found that play-based interventions could lead to substantial improvements in early math skills because they allow children to explore mathematical concepts through play actively further supports this notion, noting that hands-on learning experiences, such as those found in play-based approaches, improve cognitive outcomes by promoting exploration, experimentation, and problem-solving (Maladerita et al., 2023).

In contrast, traditional methods often involve more direct instruction and less interactive engagement, which may limit students' opportunities to actively apply what they have learned in meaningful ways. While traditional approaches may still improve learning outcomes, they are typically less effective in fostering the deep, conceptual understanding that comes from interactive, play-based learning (Nafi'ah, 2022). This was particularly relevant in the context of early childhood education, where engagement and interaction are critical for effective learning.

Furthermore, the significant difference between the two approaches in this study supported the principles of constructivist theory (Vygotsky, 1978), which argued that knowledge was constructed through active engagement with the environment and through social interaction. By providing opportunities for exploration, problem-solving, and collaboration, the play-based approach enables students to internalize mathematical concepts in ways that traditional approaches may not.

However, it was also important to note that the effectiveness of play-based learning depends on the quality of the activities and the way they are integrated into the curriculum. Play-based learning must be carefully designed and scaffolded to ensure that it is educationally valuable. If the play activities were poorly structured or lacked focus on specific learning objectives, the benefits may not be as pronounced. This may help explain why, in some educational settings, traditional methods still have a place, especially if they were well-targeted and tailored to students' needs (Widia et al., 2022).

The significant difference between the posttest scores of the participants in the traditional and play-based approaches underscored the effectiveness of the play-based approach in promoting early numeracy skills, specifically number recognition. With a mean difference of 11.5 and a highly significant p-value (<0.001), the results indicate that play-based learning leads to more substantial improvements in students' understanding of numbers compared to traditional methods. These findings were consistent with existing literature supporting the benefits of interactive, hands-on learning strategies in early childhood education (Maladerita et al., 2023; Susilawati et al., 2022).

This play-based approach appeared to offer distinct advantages over traditional teaching methods in terms of enhancing early numeracy skills. This suggested that educational practices in early childhood education should prioritize more engaging and interactive teaching approaches to foster deeper learning and achievement in foundational skills. Further studies could explore how these approaches can be further refined to ensure maximum effectiveness across diverse student populations and educational contexts.

Problem 7: What action plan can be designed based on the findings of the study?

I. Rationale

The importance of early mathematics instruction, particularly in the development of number recognition skills, cannot be overstated in the Philippine public school system. As the country's education system continues to evolve, it faces various challenges, such as large class sizes, diverse student readiness levels, and limited resources. These challenges often make it difficult to engage young learners and foster essential foundational skills. Therefore, exploring innovative teaching methods that can cater to all learners and promote better academic outcomes is crucial.

Play-based learning has gained recognition in recent years as a practical pedagogical approach, especially for early childhood education. Research has shown that play-based methods are particularly effective in subjects like mathematics, where interactive learning experiences can significantly improve student engagement and achievement. In the Philippine public education system context, where students from various socioeconomic backgrounds may have differing access to educational resources, play-based learning offers a cost-effective and engaging alternative to more traditional methods.

A recent study by Velasco (2022), which investigated the impact of non-digital game-based learning materials on Grade 2 students' mathematics achievement, supports the effectiveness of game-based and play-based approaches. Velasco found that students who used non-digital games as part of their learning activities demonstrated improved academic performance in mathematics. Specifically, the study highlighted the effectiveness of blended learning, where students engaged with both online resources and physical materials, leading to higher achievement scores in the 3rd and 4th grading periods compared to those who participated in other learning modes (e.g., modular or purely online learning).

This finding underscores the value of interactive and engaging learning experiences, which were at the core of play-based teaching methods. By introducing play-based learning into the curriculum, teachers can better engage students, particularly those who may struggle with more traditional forms of instruction. In the case of number recognition, incorporating games and hands-on activities

allows students to explore mathematical concepts in a meaningful, enjoyable way, which can lead to better retention and mastery.

This action plan proposed integrating play-based strategies into the teaching of number recognition in public elementary schools. By doing so, the goal is to help students develop strong foundational math skills in a way that was both accessible and enjoyable, ensuring that all students, regardless of background, have the opportunity to succeed in early mathematics education.

II. Objectives

Based on the study's findings, this action plan focuses more on the extreme results of the study.

To improve the teaching of number recognition by integrating play-based strategies into the existing curriculum for kindergarten.

To provide teachers with the skills and resources needed to implement play-based learning in a resource-constrained public-school environment.

To create a more engaging and inclusive learning environment that ensures all students, regardless of background, can succeed in number recognition.

To continuously monitor and assess student progress in number recognition, ensuring that teaching strategies are adjusted based on individual learning needs.

Conclusions

The findings of this study underscored the significant role that instructional methods play in early childhood education, particularly in the area of number recognition. Both the traditional and play-based approaches proved effective in improving the number recognition skills of kindergarten learners, but the play-based approach demonstrated a more profound impact on student performance. The results suggest that incorporating play-based learning strategies can enhance students' engagement, retention, and understanding of mathematical concepts.

While the traditional approach showed positive results, its impact was less pronounced than the play-based approach. This indicates that play, emphasizing exploration, creativity, and active participation, provides a more dynamic and enriching learning experience for young children. The play-based approach also aligns with current educational theories that emphasize the importance of hands-on, experiential learning, which fosters deeper cognitive engagement and a better grasp of concepts in young learners.

These findings suggest that early childhood education could benefit from a shift toward more play-based methods, especially in subjects like mathematics, where active learning and real-world applications can significantly enhance understanding. The study also emphasizes the importance of tailoring teaching strategies to young children's developmental needs and learning styles, which may require incorporating more interactive and engaging methods into the curriculum.

The following recommendations are proposed based on this study's findings and the action plan for integrating play-based learning into numeracy instruction at Kiwalan Elementary School.

Although the action plan focuses on numeracy recognition, it is recommended to gradually introduce play-based learning into other subject areas such as language, science, and even Filipino. This expansion will allow young learners to experience the benefits of hands-on, interactive learning across the curriculum, ultimately fostering a more holistic learning environment. Considering the limited resources in some rural areas, teachers can adapt low-cost or recycled materials to design engaging activities that can enhance multiple learning areas.

Professional development should be ongoing to ensure that teachers are confident and skilled in implementing play-based learning methods. In the Philippine context, in-house or district-based training workshops can be more cost-effective than external training programs. Teachers should be given opportunities for peer learning and collaborative teaching sessions where they can share best practices, learn new strategies, and support one another. The Department of Education (DepEd) can collaborate with local universities and education organizations to offer regular workshops on integrating play-based learning in early childhood education.

While integrating technology into the classroom is essential, the cost of digital tools can be a barrier in public schools, especially in rural areas. Therefore, it is recommended to incorporate low-cost digital solutions, such as educational apps that can be used on mobile phones or low-cost tablets. Community partnerships with local businesses, NGOs, or government initiatives like the DepEd's "Tech4Ed" program can provide access to affordable technology. Teachers can also use free online resources like interactive math games and videos, ensuring that play-based learning can also benefit from technological innovation.

The involvement of parents and the local community plays a vital role in the educational process. It is recommended to conduct regular workshops for parents, focusing on how they can reinforce play-based learning strategies at home using simple, accessible materials (e.g., everyday objects like bottle caps, seeds, or paper cut-outs). The PTA (Parent-Teacher Association) should also be actively involved in organizing these events and supporting school initiatives. In addition, fostering a sense of ownership in the local community through partnerships with barangay officials can provide a stronger support system for the school's play-based learning initiatives.

To ensure that the play-based learning activities are effective, it is recommended to implement ongoing formative assessments that are both simple and manageable. Teachers can use observation checklists, daily reflection logs, and short quizzes to track student progress without the need for expensive testing tools. Collaboration with local education coordinators and school heads can help establish a more standardized, but still flexible, system for monitoring students' growth. This can include using the barangay or local community for additional support in tracking students' development, especially for children who may face challenges outside the classroom.

Given the financial constraints in some areas, it is important to ensure that the play-based learning approach remains sustainable. Schools should prioritize using low-cost materials, such as recyclable items, which can be collected through community donations or local businesses. In addition, DepEd's support for play-based learning should also be emphasized in school improvement plans, with the principal working closely with the Local School Board to allocate resources and develop a long-term sustainability plan. Schools should also consider building partnerships with nearby institutions or businesses to share resources and minimize costs.

Encourage Collaboration and Resource Sharing Among Schools: In the spirit of bayanihan (community cooperation), it is recommended that Kiwalan Elementary School collaborate with neighboring schools to share ideas, materials, and strategies for implementing play-based learning. Regional DepEd offices can facilitate these efforts by organizing cluster-level meetings or workshops where teachers can exchange lesson plans, share low-cost resources, and discuss challenges and successes. Schools can also explore online platforms for resource sharing, creating a network of teachers who can work together despite geographic limitations.

Promote the Role of Play-Based Learning in Local Educational Policy: At the local level, it is essential to advocate for the inclusion of play-based learning in the school's educational plans. Teachers, school administrators, and parents should actively engage with local DepEd officials to ensure that play-based approaches are officially recognized and supported. By making play-based learning an integral part of the local educational policy, schools can receive the necessary support and recognition for their efforts to enhance early childhood education.

Evaluate and Adjust the Action Plan Based on Local Context: It is important to regularly review and adjust the play-based learning action plan to reflect the specific challenges and needs of the Kiwalan community. Teachers, school heads, and local education leaders should periodically assess the effectiveness of the activities, identify areas for improvement, and adjust the curriculum and teaching methods as needed. Regular community feedback should be sought, especially from parents and local stakeholders, to ensure that the learning activities are culturally relevant and contextually appropriate.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Sheena Mae A. Porras

St. Peter's College – Philippines

Ian G. Caliba, PhD

St. Peter's College – Philippines